
Funding sources of African no-fee open access journals

This document provides a list of funding sources of African no-fee open access (OA) journals, often referred to as Diamond OA journals. Diamond OA journals do not charge authors for publishing or readers for accessing the journals.

The list arises out of the '[Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa](#)' project, implemented by EIFL, African Journals Online (AJOL) and the West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN), with funding from Wellcome. It was collated by members of No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice, that was set up within the project, and supplements the [No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Policy Brief](#).

To illustrate the different funding sources included in the list, we provide real-life examples from institutions and journals. We acknowledge that the list is not exhaustive, and also note that most institutions and journals draw on more than one source of funding, in addition to receiving in-kind support.

Funding sources

Associations/Professional bodies membership fees and support

- [Clean Air Journal](#) is the official publication of the **National Association for Clean Air (NACA)**, a not-for-profit organisation, and publication costs are covered by the organisation for the benefit of all readers and to contribute to clean air around the world.
- **College of Surgeons of East, Central and Southern Africa** has over the past three decades supported the running of the journal [East and Central African Journal of Surgery](#) (ECAJS) on a Diamond OA model in order to allow trainees and early career surgical researchers in the region to have a platform to disseminate surgical knowledge without any publication barriers. The College provides an annual budget for the ECAJS, which includes the journal domain hosting fee, funding for the OA publishing platform, manuscript submission system, copy editing and typesetting services, and a salary for the managing editor.
- **The East African Association of Neurological Surgeons** (EAANS) has an annual budget for its [East African Journal of Neurological Sciences](#) (EAJNS), which covers essential recurrent

operating costs, including web hosting and domain renewal for the EAJNS online publishing platform, printing of hard copies of biannual journal issues, publication of the annual EAANS conference proceedings, basic administrative and logistical support, such as meeting coordination and minor communication costs. EAANS also provides strategic direction, academic support, access to a regional network of neurosurgeons and neuroscientists, promotes the journal at its annual conference and supports the peer-review process through its members.

- **Ghana Library Association** supports its [Ghana Library Journal](#) and **Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium** supports its [Journal of Information Science & Knowledge Management](#) by allocating annual budgets to cover editorial services, production costs and journal platform maintenance.
- **Groupe Interdisciplinaire de Recherche sur les Cultures et les Identités (GIRCI)** funds its [Revue Les Cahiers du GIRCI](#) with membership fees.
- **Société Médicale d'Afrique Noire de Langue Française** funds the [Dakar Médical](#) journal from annual membership fees and an annual grant from the Office of the Dean of the Faculty of Medicine, Pharmacy and Odonto-stomatology at Cheikh Anta Diop University.

Donations

- [Academicus](#) journal owned and published by **Academia de Investigação Científica** solicits online donations in addition to receiving institutional funding.
- [Journal of Food Innovation, Nutrition, and Environmental Sciences](#) accepts voluntary donations from authors and the general public to help maintain and improve the journal. On its website, the journal welcomes donations and makes it clear that donations are not linked to any specific manuscript and do not influence peer review or publication decisions in any way.

Ethical advertising

- [Clean Air Journal](#) publishes advertisements and announcements relevant to air quality and its impact in Africa. These include advertisements of companies and organisations working in this field, announcements of conferences and workshops, and relevant job listings. **NACA**, the publisher of *Clean Air Journal*, approves the advertisements that are published and this process is separate from the editorial process of the journal.

Institutional funding and support

- **Addis Ababa University** provides a fixed annual budget for its journals that covers essential resources such as office facilities, internet access, and monthly salaries for some journal editors. Other editors, editorial board members, and peer reviewers are all affiliated researchers who contribute their expertise as part of their professional engagement.

- i [*The Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*](#) is fully sustained by the OGEEES (Institute for Oil, Gas, Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development) at **Afe Babalola University**.
- i **Cheikh Anta Diop University** in Dakar Directorates and Deans award annual research and publication grants to institutes, schools, and faculties to publish their Diamond OA journals. The University Press hosts and supports Diamond OA journals.
- i **Ecole Inter-Etats des Sciences et Médecine Vétérinaires de Dakar** funds its [*Revue africaine de santé et de productions animales \(RASPA\)*](#) from its operational budget and covers the journal's editorial work and office management costs, communication, including Internet connectivity, hardware and software.
- i **Kampala International University** publications unit is a part of the Directorate of Research Innovation, Consultancy and Extension, which oversees and covers all the costs of its eight Diamond OA journals.
- i [*The Journal of Science and Technology*](#) receives institutional support from the **Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST)** to sustain its operations. The university provides dedicated office space, reliable IT infrastructure, and administrative staff, creating a stable work environment for the journal's editorial activities. Additionally, KNUST offers a consistent monthly financial contribution and allocates an annual budget to support the journal's activities.
- i **Laboratoire de botanique et Ecologie Végétale, Université de Lomé**, supports its [*Revue Ecosystèmes et Paysages*](#) by covering the costs of hosting and maintaining the journal website, connectivity and journal promotion activities (e.g. participation in scientific events). PhD students, associate professors and lecturers contribute their expertise and help run the journal. The Lomé University Press and the Research and Innovation Department provide advisory and administrative support.
- i **Mekelle University** journal [hosting platform](#) is institutionally supported by the university's Library and Research Office, which has committed resources to technical maintenance, editorial support, and policy alignment.
- i **Mzumbe University** is the host institution for the [*East African Journal of Applied Health Monitoring and Evaluation*](#) and provides financial support to assist with the journal's operations.
- i **Technical University of Mombasa** funds its [*Multidisciplinary Journal of Technical University of Mombasa*](#) through an annual budget allocated to the Department of Partnership, Research and Innovation and the University Library.
- i **Uganda Pentecostal University** supports its two Diamond OA journals with funds collected from tuition fees.
- i **Universidade Óscar Ribas** includes its [*SAPIENTIAE*](#) journal running costs in an annual institutional budget with a budget line dedicated to the maintenance and operation of the journal, covering basic editorial, publishing platform, proofreading, layout and dissemination costs.

- i **Universidade Rainha Njinga a Mbande** Publishing and Scientific Dissemination Department funds [Revista Angolana de Ciências](#) on a continuous basis and covers expenses when the need arises throughout the year (e.g. for plagiarism detection, hosting and domain name, DOIs and external editorial consultancy services).
- i **University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM)** publishes several Diamond OA journals. The custodian of all UDSM journals is the office of the Deputy Vice Chancellor – Research through the Directorate of Research and Publications. The Directorate oversees the establishment and operations of the university’s journals and delegates funding to the unit level. Diamond OA journals at UDSM are hosted on a centralized system based on the open-source software Open Journal Systems (OJS) maintained by personnel from the University’s ICT department.
- i **University of Gondar** provides the annual budget for its Diamond OA journals, which covers the monthly stipends of editors-in-chief and associate editors, technical infrastructure maintenance and web hosting, internet access and office facilities. In some cases funding is provided on an as-needed basis, drawn from the university’s research and community service budget.
- i **The University of Namibia** journal development policy supports publishing in indigenous African languages for social sciences, indigenous language and languages and literature. The university has a dedicated budget for Diamond OA journals covering subscription to typesetting software, DOI, plagiarism software, while also providing publication points for each journal issue published during promotion of academic staff who fulfil the functions of journal editors.
- i School of the Arts at the **University of Pretoria (UP)** provides a budget for its [Image & Text](#) journal and the University hosts the journal on the UP Journals platform and provides training and IT support.
- i The current strategic plan of the **University of Zambia**. includes a budget to “Enhance the efficiency of local editorial boards” for the period 2023-2027, which applies to all University journals, including Diamond OA journals.
- i **University of the Western Cape (UWC)** has provided an academic home for [New Agenda: South African Journal of Social and Economic Policy](#), published by the Institute for African Alternatives. UWC provides some funding, which enables the journal to continue as a Diamond OA journal, and the journal is published at no cost on the university’s [UWC Scholar platform](#), which is managed by the Scholarly Communication unit of the Main Library.

Multi-institutional support for learned-society journals

- i [South African Journal of Chemistry \(SAJChem\)](#) is owned by the **South African Chemical Institute (SACI)**. Funding is provided from the SACI budget to support journal operations. **The University of KwaZulu-Natal** hosts the journal management system; **Sabinet** hosts the long-term archive of the journal; SciELO SA, managed by the **Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf)**, provides indexing/hosting.
- i [South African Journal of Occupational Therapy \(SAJOT\)](#) is owned and funded by the **Occupational Therapy Association of South Africa**. Additional visibility and infrastructure is provided by ASSAf’s SciELO SA and the OA journals platform, Khulisa Journals.

Funding sources of African no-fee open access journals, February 2026

National funding and support

- Algeria:** [Algerian Scientific Journals Platform \(ASJP\)](#) that currently includes 908 Diamond OA journals and 280,583 articles, hosted by Centre de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique and funded by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, with a contribution from Direction Générale de la Recherche Scientifique et du Développement Technologique.
- Ethiopia:** [Ethiopian Journals Online \(EJOL\)](#), run by Addis Ababa University, provides free hosting for Diamond OA journals from Ethiopia, helps in setting up a journal online, provides training for editorial staff, backup, DOIs, technical support and support on OA, copyright, digitisation, visibility and other related topics, and networking opportunities.
- Morocco:** [Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal \(PRSM\)](#), with over 100 Diamond OA journals, is supported by Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique through L'Institut Marocain de l'Information Scientifique et Technique.
- South Africa:** **Academy of Science of South Africa** receives financial support from the South African Department of Science, Technology and Innovation to publish [The South African Journal of Science](#) (SAJS) and to operate and manage [SciELO SA](#) and [Khulisa Journals](#) which provide journal hosting, DOI linking; indexing of articles; preservation and archiving for South African OA journals that meet their quality criteria.
- Tunisia:** **Centre National Universitaire de Documentation Scientifique et Technique (CNUDST)** provides a framework to enhance the visibility and quality of Tunisian Diamond OA journals by providing and supporting the OJS platform, facilitating the adoption of publishing best practices focused on transparency, quality assurance and scholarly publishing standards (DOIs, metadata standardisation and compliance with OA policies).

Project funding

Journals have received project-based funding from various organisations. For example, EIFL, with funding from Wellcome, [issued two calls for proposals \(in 2024 and 2025\)](#) for improving quality and sustainability of Diamond OA journals in Africa and provided funding to 33 projects.

Research funds

Journal editors use research funds (external and internally generated) to support the journal.

Revenue generated by providing online certification courses

- Global Africa** partly supports its journal by generating revenue by providing online courses on [scientific publishing and research theories and methods in social sciences](#).

Sale of hard copies, including print on demand

- [Annales africaines de médecine](#) offers print-on-demand hard copies sales of the journal.

Research consortia

- [Global Africa](#), a pan-African interdisciplinary and multilingual journal is published by an international consortium bringing together a number of institutions with permanent member or partner member status. The consortium covers 43% of its first four-year budget and the French Development Agency provides the balance.

In addition, many Diamond OA journals benefit from free/subsidized services and support provided by publishing platforms, indexing services and research communities. Some examples are listed below.

Free/subsidised services provided by publishing platforms and indexing directories

- [African Journals Online \(AJOL\)](#) provides journal hosting and publishing, DOIs, quality assurance, training for editors/journal managers, indexing of articles, preservation and archiving.
- [African Platform for Open Scholarship](#) from the University of Cape Town provides hosting and publishing with OJS and indexing onto Google Scholar; free training and support on how to improve journal workflows.
- [Crossref](#) provides free DOIs to selected African countries.
- [DOAJ](#): an OA journal directory indexes journal content for increased visibility and [provides a preservation service](#).

Mentorship and Community of Practice (COP)

- In order to develop the skills and enhance the competences of prospective and new authors, reviewers and editors, the [Journal of Student Affairs in Africa](#) has constituted a COP that supports the journal through a variety of modalities including mentorship, professional development, webinars and virtual meetings, workshops and events. All COP involvement and events are organised on a no-cost, volunteer basis.
- The [African Health Sciences](#) journal receives mentoring supported by the [African Health Journals Partnership Project](#).

Related resources:

- Kuchma, I. (2025). Nonprofit Business Model Canvas. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14621236> [a guide that explains the use of the Nonprofit Business Model Canvas as a strategic management tool (for designing business models and operations) and provides a planning template and an [interactive whiteboard](#)]
- Melinščak Zlodi, I. (2025). Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14904444>

Authors

Members of the No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice who contributed to this document:

Assefa Chekole Addis (University of Gondar, Ethiopia) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2517-8580>

Femi Arogundade (WACREN) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9222-1817>

Aamira Bessem (CNUDST) <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0703-0840>

Wanyenda Chilimo (Technical University of Mombasa) <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8057-7405>

Iryna Kuchma (EIFL) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2064-3439>

Anna Leonard (University of Namibia) <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5237-829X>

Moira Levy (New Agenda: South African Journal of Social and Economic Policy)

Thierry M Luescher (University of Cape Town) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6675-0512>

Lighton Phiri (University of Zambia) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3582-9866>

Milica Ševkušić (EIFL) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2888-6611>

Ina Smith (Academy of Science of South Africa) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9710-3668>

Kondwani Wella (Malawi University of Science and Technology)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7506-7777>

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